

TEST AND EVALUATION OF AN IMPROVED
COLD WATER DIVING SUIT

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SUMMARY

A technical review of the Navy development program of diver thermal protection systems is presented. Topics include a discussion of the thermal requirements for the military diver, the development and application of analytical thermal modeling techniques, a review of the program progress, and a description of the configuration and testing completed on the Passive Diver Thermal Protection System. This System is currently being supplied to Fleet divers.

INTRODUCTION

Inadequate protection from cold water severely limits a military diver's ability to accomplish his mission. Advances in diving life support systems now permit the military diver to conduct long duration missions in warm water. However, in cold water a diver's physical and mental performance can be impaired and the length of a safe dive is significantly reduced. This can be a severe limitation for activities peculiar to the military diver since the location and clandestine nature of an operation often preclude surface support, and impose constraints on diver equipment.

The Naval Coastal Systems Center (NCSC) is developing diver thermal protection (DTP) equipment to satisfy the requirements of Navy and Marine Corps cold water diver/swimmers. Due to extreme differences in thermal protection required for divers using air and those using heliox mixtures, a two-part development program was established to satisfy the two needs:

1. An insulated passive garment system to provide thermal protection to divers using air or nitrogen-oxygen breathing gas mixtures.

2. Supplemental heating systems necessary for thermal protection of divers using heliox mixtures to meet their thermal protection needs.

Providing adequate thermal insulation to the diver's body is difficult because of the underwater operating environment. In man's usual environment of air, the insulation provided by clothing is largely due to trapped gas. In water, however, the insulating layer of gas is lost. Moreover, water has a thermal conductivity nearly 25 times that of air. The heat capacity of water (product of density and specific heat) is approximately 3500 times that of air. Consequently, body heat is lost much faster in water than in air of the same temperature.

Performance Requirements

The Navy diver's activities range from the support of salvage operations to the clandestine attack of enemy assets. The operational requirements and typical mission scenarios were studied to identify the salient characteristics pertaining to thermal protection for the various missions. Some of the

factors considered were diver activity level, or metabolic rate; depth; breathing gas composition; environmental factors, dive duration; life support system used; mission-related equipment used; and the actual tasks the diver must perform¹. The most severe exposure identified was a 6-hour dive in 4.5°C (40°F) water at low to moderate work rates.

Along with the operational requirements, it was necessary to establish criteria to define the thermal limits for a diver to accomplish his objective and return safely. These criteria were developed by a panel of experts on thermal physiology headed by Dr. Paul Webb² for the Navy Bureau of Medicine and Surgery and summarized in Table 1.

TABLE 1

PHYSIOLOGICAL DESIGN GOALS
FOR THERMAL PROTECTION OF DIVERS

1. Maximum net body heat loss (change in enthalpy) of 3 kcal per kg of body weight.
2. Core temperature not lower than 36°C (96.8°F), or a 1°C (1.8°F) drop, whichever is lower.
3. Mean skin temperature not lower than 25°C (77°F), and no individual skin temperature lower than 20°C (68°F), except that of the hand, which may go as low as 15°C (59°F).

These criteria established a basis for an engineering development program with the operational requirements defining what the diver must perform and the thermal limits defining the allowed thermal stress.

Passive System Development

The system development activities were predicated on establishing an analytical model of the suited diver in the cold water environment, refining this model by incorporating the results of testing, and then using the model to determine the necessary thermal design characteristics of the final system. Previous testing at NCSC and elsewhere^{3,4,5} showed that wet suits could not be expected to satisfy the thermal protection requirements and that variable volume dry suits were the preferred approach.

A wide selection of commercially available dry suit systems were obtained and subjected to extensive evaluations. Tests included: the evaluation of materials and construction features by the Navy Textile and Clothing Research Facility⁶; Range of Motion and Mobility Characteristics by the Department of Kinesiology at the University of California at Los Angeles⁷; thermal properties at 1 ata using a thermal manikin by the Army Institute of Environmental Medicine (ARIEM)⁸; and extensive evaluations by Navy divers to evaluate the operational characteristics of the various garment systems.⁹

NCSC and ARIEM also used the copper manikin to test three dry suit models in combination with five types of undergarments under hyperbaric conditions.¹⁰ Ten configurations were tested to simulated depths of 16 ata (atmospheres absolute) with nitrogen and helium used as suit inflation gases. Prior to these tests NCSC developed an analytical model for predicting the thermal properties of diving suit materials at surface and hyperbaric conditions.¹¹ The test results differed slightly from predicted values, requiring modification of the assumptions used in the analytical thermal model.

The copper manikin tests found that none of the dry suits or dry suit/undergarment ensembles had enough insulation to satisfy the required thermal criteria and performance goals.

The tests, as predicted, showed 1) significantly less insulation at all depths when helium was used as the suit system's inflation gas due to the thermal properties of the helium, itself. 2) All neoprene foam dry suit/undergarment ensembles had a reduction of insulation with depth, with greatest insulation loss occurring in the first 4 ata of depth. 3) Coated-fabric dry suit/undergarment ensembles showed no reduction in insulation with depth since there was no closed cell foam to compress.

The testing and evaluation of commercial equipment revealed the need for an engineering development program to obtain equipment to protect divers in cold water for missions up to 6 hours. This commercial equipment evaluation also demonstrated the most successful approaches to thermal protection.

Passive Diver Thermal Protection System (PDTPS) Description

A discussion of the design of a dry suit system which would best meet the Navy's needs as given in Table 2 can be found in references 12 and 13. The Passive DTP System (PDTPS) is a modular variable-volume dry suit system. A flexible water-tight outer-garment keeps the diver dry. Inlet and exhaust valves are used to control the suit inflation level. Thermal insulation is provided by high performance insulating underwear worn over a cotton long-john comfort layer and socks. Dry gloves with insulating liners keep the diver's hands warm.

Outer-garment

The outer-garment is made from a foam neoprene elastomer specially processed to permanently eliminate the gas-filled cell structure found in wet suits. A knitted nylon fabric is bonded to both sides of the material. A hood, boots, neck seal, wrist seals, and wrist rings are integral to the outer-garment. The outer-garment is equipped with calf and thigh restraints, ankle straps, and calf weight pockets. A water-tight zipper from the left shoulder across the front to the right hip facilitates diver entry. Front and back views of a diver wearing the PDTPS are shown in Figures 1 and 2.

Inflation gas inlet and exhaust valves penetrate the outer-garment. These permit the diver to control the amount of inflation gas in his suit to provide buoyancy control and partial control over his suit insulation.

Thermal Under-garment

The under-garment provides most of the system insulation and consists of three components: jacket,

TABLE 2

REQUIRED PERFORMANCE CHARACTERISTICS OF A DRY SUIT		
Requirement	Threshold	Goal
Insulation equivalence	1.0 clo*	1.2 clo*
Net body heat loss	3 kcal/kg of body weight	3 kcal/kg of body weight
Range of motion (% of nude mobility)	85%	85%
Dive duration**	6 hours	6 hours
Low temperature limit	40°F (4.4°C)	29°F (-1.7°C)
Maximum depth	200 fsw (61.0 msw)	300 fsw (91.4 msw)
Maximum descent rate	30 ft/min (9.1 m/min)	60 ft/min (18.3 m/min)
Maximum ascent rate	60 ft/min (18.3 m/min)	60 ft/min (18.3 m/min)

These performance characteristics apply only when air or a mixture of nitrogen and oxygen is used for suit inflation.

*Clo is a measure of insulation such that 1 clo = 0.18 m²-hr-°C/kcal. One clo of insulation will maintain normal skin temperature of the human body when heat production is 50 kcal per square metre per hour (normal heat production of a man at rest), air temperature is 70°F (21.1°C) and the air is still. A standard 0.25-inch wet suit has an approximate value of 0.75 clo water at the surface.

**When the diver sustains a moderate level of physical activity.

pants, and thermal boots. The insulating material is a microfibrinous polyolefin batt. This material insulates well for its low weight and bulk, and is relatively compression- and water-resistant. Nylon taffeta is used as an outer layer, and neoprene-coated nylon taffeta is used as the inner layer. The inner coating forms a moisture- and vapor-resistant barrier. The thermal undergarment is worn over a comfort liner of long johns and socks. (Figure 2.)

Dry Gloves

The dry gloves seal onto the outer-garment at the wrist rings where they are secured with an elastic strap. Each glove has a thermal liner insulated with a material similar to that used in the under-garment.

Other Components

Other accessory components were developed to complement the performance capabilities of the dry suit system. These include an independent suit inflation source, inflation hoses, a Diver Urine Collection System (DUCS), for long duration missions, fin guards to facilitate putting on the fins and to prevent their loss, a thermally insulated cap, and a cold weather face protector. (Figure 3.)

Prototype Development Tests

To demonstrate that the passive DTP system could meet the operational requirements of diver missions, a number of specific and combined tests were conducted in the field and at test facilities^{14,15}. These evaluations confirmed the basic thermal design and led to a number of changes which improved field use of the system. The final configuration of the suit system underwent substantial testing and evaluation to ensure that it met all operational requirements.

FIGURE 1. DIVER IN PDPTS

THERMAL CAP

COLD WEATHER FACE
PROTECTOR

FIN GUARDS

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 2 COMFORT LINER
AND DUCS

THERMAL
UNDERGARMENT

Field Testing - Panama City

A series of tests was conducted during December 1979 to evaluate the performance of the prototype of the passive DTP system in special warfare type activities. Tests included realistic simulations of three typical SPECWAR activities: (1) long-distance surface swim, (2) long-distance submerged swim, and (3) helicopter cast and recovery.

The 2000-yard surface and submerged swims were accomplished without difficulty. The surface swim was followed by cast and recovery of two divers at 10 and 15 knots from an inflatable boat tied alongside a 35-foot utility boat, without problems. The helicopter cast was performed at a nominal 15-knot forward speed 15 feet above the surface. Both divers' glove seals separated upon impact with the water; improved seals and glove exhaust valves would prevent this. Recovery was accomplished via Jacob's ladder to the hovering helicopter without incident.

The system was also tested in two Free-Flooding Submersible (FFS) runs of approximately 3 hours each during February 1980 in St. Andrew Bay, Florida. Water temperatures were approximately 42°F (5.6°C). Two divers used suits with improved wrist and neck seals and experienced no leaks. Extensive and re-

peated suit modifications resulted in seam leaks and leaks around a valve port. However, due to the water resistant properties of the thermal under-garment the divers remained warm and experienced no difficulty with suit inflation affecting FFS trim.

These tests finalized the system design baseline for subsequent operational development tests in which both UDT and SEAL team personnel participated.

FIGURE 4. HIGH-SPEED CAST OF DIVER FROM INFLATABLE BOAT

Field Testing - Brunswick, Maine; New London, Connecticut

System tests and evaluations were conducted by NCSC and NEDU personnel at the Casco Bay Naval Fuel Farm, NAS Brunswick, Maine. Eight swimmer-evaluators were provided by NAVSPECWARGRU TWO. Casco Bay normally has cool air and water temperatures. However, unseasonably warm weather with air temperatures up to 90°F (32.2°C) caused problems of diver overheating and affected some planned operations. Water temperatures at the surface were in the range of 59°F to 72°F (15°C to 22°C) and 53°F to 58°F (11.6°C to 14.4°C) at depths below 5 feet.

These tests were intended to demonstrate that the system satisfies operational objectives in simulated mission scenarios. The compatibility of the system with other diving equipment was an important aspect of the evaluations. Accordingly, the PDTPS was used with the MK 4 life vest, the MK 15 UBA, SCUBA, and parachutes.

The System was tested in the following operations to demonstrate compliance with design requirements.

1. Long Distance Surface Swim
2. Long Distance Submerged Swim
3. High Speed Boat Cast and Recovery
4. Parachute Jump
5. Helicopter Cast and Recovery

Procedures and results for each test are described in the following paragraphs.

Long Distance Surface Swim. Eight divers swam approximately 2 miles using the System and only ankle weights. The air temperature was approximately 80°F (26.7°C) and the surface water temperature was approximately 70°F (21°C). Problems experienced were

overheating and minor difficulty moving the arm forward while performing the side stroke.

Long Distance Submerged Swim. Twenty 4000-yard (3658 m) swims with SCUBA at depths not greater than 30 feet (9 metres) were made. Divers complained of lack of mobility in the arms and shoulders, and difficulty reaching the SCUBA reserve valve. Initially, divers complained of a pressure point on each ankle created by the 3-pound ankle weights.

High Speed Boat Cast and Recovery. Using a 41-foot Coast Guard Cutter with an inflatable boat attached to the side, seven divers were cast (Fig. 4) at approximately 100-foot (30.5-metre) intervals and recovered using the snare. This procedure was repeated four times at speeds ranging from 8 to 14 knots. On the first recovery one exhaust valve was broken off by contact with the snare. The force of the water on cast rolled back the upper portion of the glove, separating the seal and causing glove leakage.

Parachute Jump. (Fig. 5) Four parachute jumps were accomplished from altitudes of 1200 to 1500 feet (366 to 457 metres) with helicopter air speed of approximately 70 knots. Water impact was uneventful with no suit leaks reported. The upper portion of some glove seals was pulled down from contact with the suspension lines while divers removed the parachute harness in the water. Several divers complained that the location of the exhaust valve impeded removing the harness; two complained of a lack of upper arm and shoulder mobility and inability to reach the parachute steering toggles.

Helicopter Cast and Recovery. Two lifts of four divers each were performed for a total of eight casts and recoveries. Altitude of the helicopter was approximately 15 feet (4.5 metres) and speed approximately 15 knots. All divers successfully

FIGURE 5. DIVERS EQUIPPED WITH PARACHUTES OUTFITTED IN PDTPS

climbed a Jacob's ladder back into the aircraft. (Figure 6)

At the conclusion of the testing, the evaluation forms prepared by each diver for each operation were statistically summarized with the prototype system receiving a rating between acceptable and good. A number of suggestions for changes were made which were used to modify the prototype configuration.

Tests at Navy Experimental Diving Unit NEDU, Panama City, Florida

Range of Motion Tests were performed on the modified prototypes with a rating of 90.1 percent nude mobility achieved.

Rapid compression and decompression tests were performed to demonstrate that the system satisfied the requirement for maximum ascent and descent rate listed in Table 2.

Field Testing - Whidbey Island

The purpose of these exercises, conducted at NAS, Whidbey Island, Washington, was to determine the practicality of using the PDTPS with the Free Flooding Submersible (FFS) and to provide training for Free Flooding Submersible operators from Underwater Demolition Team-12 in preparation for Exercise Brim Frost. The systems used for this activity were the same units used at Casco Bay in July.

Two FFS platoons participated in these exercises. Approximately 29 man-hours of FFS operations were accomplished. Surface water temperatures were between 39 and 42°F (4 and 5.5°C), and air temperatures between 27 and 50°F (3 and 10°C). Dive time during several FFS operations was limited by the safety boat's ability to operate in the surface chop and not by the thermal status of the FFS operators.

Buoyancy in the upper torso of the suit made it difficult for operators to lean forward to operate FFS controls. This problem was resolved by using modified integrated diving vests under the MK 4 life preserver, thus restraining the upper portion of the suit.

During this testing the necessity for a number of minor but important modifications became evident to improve the compatibility between the suit system, the FFS, and the MK 15 Underwater Breathing Apparatus. These included the relocation of the inlet valve to the top of the left thigh, increasing the cracking pressure of the glove vent valve, providing a urine dump line, and wrist seal changes to improve wear characteristics.

Exercises at this site increased confidence in the capability of the PDTPs to function properly in an operational environment.

Positive Buoyancy Tests - NEDU, Panama City, Florida

Prior to FFS operations scheduled as part of the Kodiak Island tests, a test was performed at the NEDU Ocean Simulation Facility Test Pool to determine if the PDTPS offered sufficient positive buoyancy to allow diver free ascent.

Two divers were outfitted in the PDTPS, Integrated Diving Vest, SCUBA (bled down until neutrally buoyant), weight belt, and maximum calf weights. Fins and life jackets were not worn in order to better approximate conditions of an FFS operation. After intentionally flooding their suits, the divers

dropped their weight belts only and attempted to surface. Both kicked to the surface with ease, demonstrating the inherent positive buoyancy of the polyolefin batt thermal under-garment material. In the unlikely event of simultaneous PDTPS floodout and MK 15 UBA and MK 4 life jacket failures, a diver may exit an FFS and ascend safely by dropping his weight belt.

Field Testing - Kodiak Island, Alaska

The objective of this activity was to facilitate special warfare missions during exercise Brim Frost and further evaluate system performance in simulated scenarios. Five systems with a new configuration outer-garment were used. Three systems of the prior configuration were taken as spares along with various accessory items. The new outer-garment configuration incorporated modifications made after testing at Casco Bay and Whidbey Island: improved seaming technique, redesigned wrist seals, a redesigned foot and ankle restraint area, incorporation of pockets for the ankle weights in the calf restraints, tall as well as regular sizes, and relocation of the inflation valve to the top of the left thigh. Gloves with a new seal configuration were provided in addition to units of the prior configuration. Polyolefin batt caps and glove liners, face protectors, and urine collection systems with overboard dump lines were included as accessories for extremely cold water.

FIGURE 6. HELICOPTER RECOVERING DIVER USING JACOB'S LADDER

During the tests, surface water temperatures were 36 to 39°F (2.2 to 3.8°C) and air temperatures 25 to 45°F (-3.9 to 7.2°C). Colder water temperatures were reported below the surface. A total of 11 1/2 hours of FFS runs were made using the system with no unacceptable levels of cold stress or reports of inadequate performance due to the cold water. During the longest exposure, the FFS pilot and navigator spent approximately 5 hours in water estimated to be 34°F (1°C) with no problems.

Although the system was intended for use only by the five FFS operators in the second platoon of UDT 12, three SEAL personnel were also trained and equipped to use the system. A 5-hour SEAL and FFS operation was completed by two divers involving insertion and recovery of the SEALs and their weapons from the FFS, landing on a rocky beach area and pitching a four-man tent. There were no major problems with the suit system.

There were two minor equipment problems which would require system modification. The new configuration boots did not provide adequate traction on ice, snow, and rock; and the diver's heels tended to slip out of the boot. A design change to provide a harder sole with tread and a relocated ankle strap was indicated. The glove seal configuration allowed only a limited number of uses before the hard vinyl edge of the wrist ring caused ruptures in the neoprene foam seal. A design change covering the vinyl wrist ring with large diameter dual O-rings has corrected the problem. The final change was to relocate the zippered entry from across the shoulders to the front of the garment which greatly improved the arm/shoulder mobility. During tests, these modifi-

cations proved successful. The new zipper location allows unassisted donning and provides mobility close to that afforded by a wet suit. At the conclusion of the testing described above, the system was considered to have satisfied the original requirements shown in Tables 1 and 2 and to have demonstrated its ability to accommodate a wide range of activities peculiar to the military diver.

Approval for Navy use was granted in April 1982. The system is now being used by Special Warfare Units, Underwater Construction Teams, and Explosive Ordnance Disposal divers and has successfully eliminated much of the thermal stress associated with cold water diving.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. NCSC TM 378-83, "Development of Passive Diver Thermal Protection System," M. W. Lippitt, Jr., and M. L. Nuckols, May 1983.
2. "Physiological Design Goals for Thermal Protection of Divers," prepared for the Naval Medical Research and Development Command by Webb Associates, Yellow Springs, Ohio, September 1980.
3. NCSL 223-74, "Gas Consumption of SCUBA Divers," M. W. Lippitt, Jr., and G. F. Bond, CAPT (MC), USN, October 1974.
4. NCSL 271-76, "Improved Thermal Protection and Rewarm Procedures for Cold Water Divers," M. W. Lippitt, Jr. and G. F. Bond, CAPT (MC) USN, February 1976.
5. Goldman, R. F., et al., "'Wet' Versus 'Dry' Suit Approaches to Water Immersion Protective Clothing," *Aerospace Medicine*, Volume 37, No. 5, May 1966.
6. Andruk, Frances S., "Inspection of Commercial Dry-Type Diver's Suits," Navy Clothing and Textile Research Facility, letter report for Work Request N61331-76-WR-T-002, November 1976.
7. Egstrom, Glen H., et al., "Comparative Mobility in Various Dry Suits," Dept. Kinesiology, Univ. of Calif. (LA), Contract No. N61331-76-M-4166, September 1976 for NCSL.
8. US Army, Report No. T 1/81, "Thermal Protection of Commercial Dry Suit Diving Systems," ARIEM, 14 January 1981.
9. NCSC TM 241-78, "Human Engineering Evaluation of Dry Suits for Navy Use," F. Wattenbarger and LT J. Brady, October 1978.
10. Wattenbarger, J. F., and J. R. Breckenridge, "Dry Suit Insulation Characteristics Under Hyperbaric Conditions," American Society of Mechanical Engineers publication OED-Volume 6, pages 101-116, 1978.
11. Nuckols, M. L., "Thermal Considerations in the Design of Diver's Suits," American Society of Mechanical Engineers publication OED-Volume 6, pages 83-99, 1978.
12. NCSC TM 281-80, "The Development of Thermal Undergarments for Diver's Dry Suit," M. L. Nuckols, May 1980.
13. NCSC TM 336-82, "The Development of an Improved Suit System for Cold Water Diving," Maxwell W. Lippitt, Jr., and Marshall L. Nuckols, February 1982.
14. US Navy, Navy Experimental Diving Unit Report 13-79, "Manned Evaluation of the NCSC Diver Thermal Protection (DTP) Passive System Prototype," by C. A. Piantadosi, D. J. Ball, M. L. Nuckols and E. D. Thalmann, August 1979.
15. US Navy, Navy Experimental Diving Unit Report 10-81, "Manned Evaluation of an Improved Passive Diver Thermal Protection System," by J. L. Zumrick.